

reunește un interviu ce are ca subiect viața documentelor păstrate (sau abandonate) în Arhivele Naționale de Film Sahia și un text ce contrapunctează problematica primului, punând în discuție o arhivă în pragul abandonului, cea de fotografii a Fabricii de Mobilă din Iași. Ambele texte, în fapt studii de caz, vorbesc despre abandonul arhivei, mai precis al memoriei și despre cauzele (politice, sociologie, sau cultural-istorice) care generează acest fel de abandon.

Dar tocmai datorită perspectivelor diverse din care numărul 24 al revistei Martor abordează problema procesului de arhivare ca fenomen al societăților contemporane, sunt evidențiate formele hibride ce caracterizează astăzi acest fenomen, forme datorate nu numai contextului tehnologic, dar inevitabil și celui politic sau economic cu toate implicațiile etico-juridice care rezultă de aici.

Volumul se încheie cu trei recenzii, prima dedicată unei colecții de CD-uri ce valorifică documente inedite (documentare, filme utilitare din perioada 1960–1980) aflate în Arhivele Sahia, celelalte două atrăgând atenția asupra două cărți dedicate unor colecții de obiecte integrate unor arhive) contextualizează mai larg tematica revistei: una semnată de Inge Daniels, *What are Exhibitions for? An Anthropological Approach* (2019), iar cealaltă de Alexandra Urdea *From Storeroom to Stage: Romanian Attire and the Politics of Folklore* (2018).

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Sándor Varga, *Two Traditional Central Transylvanian Dances and Their Economic and Cultural/Political Background*, in “Acta Ethnographica Hungarica” vol. 65, issue 1, 2020, p. 39–64.

There have been numerous debates over time as to the origin of the names of some dance types, in the Romanian and foreign scientific communities. It is well known that over the centuries, the Romanians and the minorities of several ethnicities lived together in a beneficial symbiosis in Transylvania. Some traditions and customs were adopted by both sides and finished to be considered as ‘local’, having a direct influence upon socialising. The names of these cultural elements and many words from the current vocabulary were borrowed and lent at the same time by the Romanians and the minorities, thus resulting in a new vocabulary. The people took over and used these words with the desire of having an interethnic communication, and being ‘closer to the soul’.

Starting from this hypothesis, we read *Two Traditional Central Transylvanian Dances and Their Economic and Cultural/Political Background*, written by Sándor Varga, researcher of the Department of Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology in Szeged. The author refers to two forms of kinetic expressions named ‘Haidău’ – ‘Hajdútánc’ and ‘Tárnăveana’ – ‘Korcsos’. The two dances have been and still are danced in the Plain of

Transylvania by Romanian and the Hungarian minority, the latter having other names for the two types of dance. Published in *Acta Ethnographica Hungarica* no. 65/1/2020, the paper contains an introduction to the theme, an overview of stick dances from the area mentioned above, an analysis of political and economic changes and their influences on the life and traditional culture of the region, a description of the 'Tárnăveana' dance process.

The source cited by the author is mainly Martin György (with his study from 1980). The author cites him referring to the beginning of the research of the Romanian dance type Haidău (Hajdú), which he connects with the other dances specific to shepherds. The same cited source appreciates in the conclusion of the article the uniqueness of this dance category, developed in Transylvania before the 18th century. The Romanian researchers cited are Anca Giurchescu, Constantin Costea and Zamfir Dejeu¹. The first two Romanian researchers take this idea further and make connections with the dances using accessories (sticks, swords, etc) from the European and Romanian cultural area, connecting also to the excerpts of Sándor Varga about the rituals of 'Căluș' and the 'Călușeri' dances from Transylvania (which as we know are a part of an archaic cultural base). The important areas from Transylvania brought to light are the ones where the 'Călușeri' dances have appeared and then disappeared². These areas are analysed starting from the central part of Transylvania towards the Southern part, more precisely from the area of Mureș to the area of Târnavă, regions where dancers were performing using a stick. A conclusion of the author introduces us to the 'high point' of his study, which unravels the problems that influenced the disappearance and reappearance of these dances in Transylvania.

The political and economical changes (the redistributions of lands and the division of individual and collective properties) have had a great impact on the organisation of communities. To complete the image of the adopted reforms and politics starting with the 19th century in the Plain of Transylvania, and the image of the main professions, several pieces of information from the researches Bertalan Andrásfalvy and Károly Kós are presented. Above all, the main profession which stands out is shepherding³, presented in relation to the lands/properties where this profession was practiced (with all its traditions). The reforms analysis outlines the low character of the elected people working in administrative public institutions and the socio-cultural consequences. The landowners and noblemen of the time influenced the communities way of organising and, implicitly, the way of organising the dance in central areas. The shepherds' migration and transhumance helped the transfer of the dances to the areas where they were moving. The references about the Romanian shepherds from the Plain of Transylvania and, through a comparative analysis, from 'Valea Bistrei' have an important contribution to the explaining and understanding of the socio-cultural situation in the 19th and 20th centuries.

In his research, the author wishes to point out the way the shepherds' dance came into the repertoire of villages, relying on Martin György's affirmations, who states that the dances with accessories were also implemented in the case of pig breeders.

¹ In the 2nd part where he refers to the dances from the category 'Fecioresc rar' - 'Tárnăveană'.

² Due to certain political occurrences hereinafter presented.

³ Because stick dances have their origin in this profession.

An interesting conclusion of the author, worth to be mentioned, is that the dances with weapons disappeared during World War I.

Sándor Varga thinks that the dances with accessories from Transylvania, 'De bătă' (stick dance) and 'Călușer', survived because of the public policies adopted in the area and due to the dance instructors who managed their revival after World War II. This opinion is supported by the arguments about the creations of the Romanian people in the mid-19th century, which emphasize the character of these dance types and the direction of the Romanian choreographic culture.

Romanian authors analysed different aspects of shepherd dances⁴ from much earlier periods. "[...] The choreographers consider that many traditional dances have their origin in the shepherd environment, like for example: 'Brăul', 'Sârba', 'Bătuta' and so on. The shepherd dance, along with other dance types flourished in the Middle Ages (especially in the 15th-18th centuries), being a central part of the traditional culture as a whole. Moreover, because of the intense movement of shepherds' beyond country borders and the identity of lifestyle, a commune artistic background has crystallised, and dance is a part of it. In terms of choreography, shepherds' dances – as hajduk dances which have common traits – are characterised by the virtuosity and difficulty of execution, accompanied by objects used in day-to-day activities (the stick, the axe, etc.). Shepherds dances are men's group dances. The shepherds' dance was well known and appreciated at the courts of feudal lords in the neighbouring countries. The Austrian Ambassador from Constantinople admires the dance in Bratislava, in the 16th century; In the 11th century the dance is attested in the Balkan nations, and later in Czechoslovak Carpathians. Sulzer makes a classification and notices the great value of the dances named 'mocănești' or 'cătănești' (going to the army lad's dances). The music for these dances was performed using a flute ('fluiet' in Romanian) or bagpipes, which, together with the 'bucium' (a type of alphorn) contributed to the ethnical melody.⁵ "The melody⁶ is still kept in the living vocabulary of the Romanian people as 'Bătuta' (in Bihor), 'Călușeriu' (in Țara Moșilor), as for the Gorals in the South of Poland."⁷

In the last part of his work, Sándor Varga highlights the most important thing, supported by the quotes of Martin György according to which the mixed communities have the most complex repertoire. This is due to the inevitable 'competitive' process and the influences of two or more different cultures in the process of dance evolution.

Nonetheless, as we stated before, we consider that the different names of dances refer to the actors (dancers) who dance them. Thus, 'lassú legényes' was "[...] mainly performed by Hungarians, and 'Românește' or 'Românește de ponturi' was mainly danced by Romanians". The information offered by the author is based on the opinions of some people who were interviewed, but we are not quite sure that only one source, in most cases, can offer clear suggestions in defining some terms. The opinion according to which the dance 'Târnavăana' would come from the area 'zona Târnavelor' can be just

⁴ Shepherd dance repertory.

⁵ Emilia Comișel, *Folclor muzical*, București, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, 1967, p. 248.

⁶ Emilia Comișel make a reference to the Haiducky song, found in the Tablature of Jan of Lublin (1540), which identifies in present times with a variant of the dance named 'Banu Mărăcine'/'Călușar'.

⁷ Emilia Comișel, *op. cit.*, p. 17.

an assumption, based in the first place on the phonetic construction of the words. An opposed conclusion was launched by dr. Zamfir Dejeu from the Folklor Archive of the Romanian Academy: “The most frequent name for ‘Feciorescul rar’ in binary rhythm is Târnavăana. Though, it is curious that in the area ‘zona Târnavă’ this dance is not danced.”⁸ This statement can be considered for further detailed analysis.

Another important fact revealed by the reviewed study is the correlation of old and new information. Thus, it is improbable that this phenomenon started from only one direction regarding the mapping. The two cultures are resemblant, and they influenced each other over time, each of them trying to stand out through certain techniques, which were most of the times opposite/different, as pointed out by the quotes of G. Martin. The researcher does not stop here and brings to our attention several quotes of Hungarian researchers who, probably ignorantly or inadvertently, omitted in their research the correct use of terminology as to the names of dances. We are led towards a critical heads-up, attributed to these researchers publications from the second half of the 20th century.

The author of the article tries to keep a balance between the two scientific ‘sides’, recognising the importance of the UNESCO decision in 2015 to the Romanian lad’s dance.

In the end, with a decent subtlety, the author exposes an important idea, through which the perspectives of the article is shaping up. “Increased financial support for the national minority across the border, manifest in a growing number of festivals, folk art camps and media coverage show that Hungarian as well as Romanian cultural policy not only supports folk art as a community-building and artistic activity but also uses it as a tool of propaganda. [...] depends on the political-social attitude towards the audience.”

Through his analysis, Sándor Varga contributes to the clarification of a reality viewed from a different point of view – politically, economically and culturally – mentioning that his endeavour can be unequivocally considered an anthropological study. The article contains numerous citations of researchers, and that is why the analysis deserves to be studied by experts in the fields of interest. The author concludes, bringing together historical, political, anthropological, folklorical, and folkloristic studies, pointing out first-class information regarding the terminology, through focused quotes on the subject: “In the course of presenting traditional folklore on the stage as folklorism, the past is depicted as the present, giving an image of continuity. [...] Conversely, in the context of a stage performance even the closest reproduction of a folklore model remains an imitation.”⁹ The opposing views of other researchers regarding the origin of these dances are to be analysed in a scientific context, with clear evidence, meant to fill in these gaps. At the moment, a conclusion sustaining that Anca Giurchescu would have stated that ‘Haidău’ dance has another origin than the Romanian one would stir up controversies in the Romanian political and cultural scientific community at the same time¹⁰. This is why we consider that the opinions of the researchers who have previously

⁸ Zamfir Dejeu, *Jocul Fecioresc din România*, Editura Fundației pentru Studii Europene, Cluj-Napoca, 2016, p. 169–170.

⁹ Anca Giurchescu, *The Power of Dance and Its Social and Political Uses*, in „Yearbook for Traditional Music”, vol. 33, 2001, Cambridge University Press, p. 117.

¹⁰ This is precisely why we consider that the importance of an extensive bibliography (see the following footnotes) of the subjects analysed should come first in an attempt of a ‘reconstitution’ of reality, especially

spoken on this subject must be presented with objectivity, avoiding misinterpretation or misunderstanding of their opinions.

The bibliography sources used by the author for his article are mostly Hungarian. The bibliography contains also a few Romanian and international sources.

We consider that the opinion of dr. Zamfir Dejeu according to which: “In our days, the dance ‘Haidăul’ is only known to be the one having a Rondo shape, with ample movements.”¹¹, as well as the opinion already cited regarding the name of Feciorescul rar/Tărnăveană, which could bring nuance to the conclusions of this analysis.

Some of the papers we consider would bring added value to Sándor Varga’s contribution are Romanian materials published in *Revista de etnografie și folclor*, in 1962¹², 1967¹³, 1966¹⁴, 1963¹⁵, 1995¹⁶, 1987–1988¹⁷. We consider that the approach of the subjects presented in *Revista de etnografie și folclor* is an objective one, based on the reality of lad’s dances from Transylvania in the 19th and 20th centuries.

The contribution of this research in the ethnochoreology scientific domain is auspicious, especially if we think of the perspective it offers. Analysing the political and social contexts and their influence on the dances is another way to understand the evolution in time, not only of the society but of the cultural practice in different areas where two or more types of culture are present.

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considering that the article analyses two types of dances protected by the UNESCO decision mentioned above, which certifies the communities that have danced and continue to dance these dances.

¹¹ Z. Dejeu, *op. cit.*

¹² Anca Giurchescu și Constantin Costea, *Haidăul*, în „Revista de etnografie și folclor”, anul VII, 1962, nr. 1–2.

¹³ Andrei Bucșan, *Contribuții la studiul jocurilor călușerești*, în „Revista de etnografie și folclor”, tom 21, 1976, nr. 1.

¹⁴ Idem, *Jocuri de Circulație pastorală*, în „Revista de etnografie și folclor”, tom 11, 1966, nr. 3.

¹⁵ A. Giurchescu, *Jocurile ciobănești din satul Dumbrava*, în „Revista de etnografie și folclor”, an VIII, 1963, nr.3–4.

¹⁶ Herbert Hoffman, *Dansul Popular românesc „călușar” în context european*, în „Revista de etnografie și folclor”, tom 40, 1995, nr. 2.

¹⁷ Constantin Costea, *Jocurile feciorești transilvănene (atestări documentare)*, în „Revista de etnografie și folclor”, tom 32–33, 1987–1988, nr.1.